

The Characteristic Function of a Neutrosophic Set

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Abstract. The purpose of this paper is to introduce and study the characteristic function of a neutrosophic set. After given the fundamental definitions of neutrosophic set operations generated by the characteristic function of a neutrosophic set (for short), we obtain several properties, and discussed the relationship between

neutrosophic sets generated by N_g and others. Finally, we introduce the neutrosophic topological spaces generated by . Possible application to GIS topology rules are touched upon.

Keywords: Neutrosophic Set; Neutrosophic Topology; Characteristic Function.

1 Introduction

Neutrosophy has laid the foundation for a whole family of new mathematical theories generalizing both their classical and fuzzy counterparts, such as a neutrosophic set theory. After the introduction of the neutrosophic set concepts in [2-13]. In this paper we introduce definitions of neutrosophic sets by characteristic function. After given the fundamental definitions of neutrosophic set operations by , we obtain several properties, and discussed the relationship between neutrosophic sets and others. Added to, we introduce the neutrosophic topological spaces generated by N_g .

2 Terminologies

We recollect some relevant basic preliminaries, and in particular, the work of Smarandache in [7- 9], Hanafy, Salama et al. [2- 13] and Demirci in [1].

3 Neutrosophic Sets generated by N_g

We shall now consider some possible definitions for basic concepts of the neutrosophic sets generated by and its operations.

3.1 Definition

Let X is a non-empty fixed set. A neutrosophic set

(NS for short) A is an object having the form $A = \langle x, \mu_A(x), \sigma_A(x), \nu_A(x) \rangle$ where $\mu_A(x)$, $\sigma_A(x)$ and $\nu_A(x)$ which represent the degree of member ship function (namely $\mu_A(x)$), the degree of indeterminacy (namely $\sigma_A(x)$), and the degree of non-member ship (namely $\nu_A(x)$) respectively of each element $x \in X$ to the set A .and let $g_A : X \times [0,1] \rightarrow [0,1] = I$ be reality function,

then $N_{g_A}(\lambda) = N_{g_A}(\langle x, \lambda_1, \lambda_2, \lambda_3 \rangle)$ is said to be the characteristic function of a neutrosophic set on X if

$$N_{g_A}(\lambda) = \begin{cases} 1 & \text{if } \mu_A(x) = \lambda_1, \sigma_A(x) = \lambda_2, \nu_A(x) = \lambda_3 \\ 0 & \text{otherwise} \end{cases}$$

Where $\lambda = \langle x, \lambda_1, \lambda_2, \lambda_3 \rangle$. Then the object

$G(A) = \langle x, \mu_{G(A)}(x), \sigma_{G(A)}(x), \nu_{G(A)}(x) \rangle$ is a

neutrosophic set generated by where

$$\mu_{G(A)} = \sup \lambda_1 \{N_{g_A}(\lambda) \wedge \lambda\}$$

$$\sigma_{G(A)} = \sup \lambda_2 \{N_{g_A}(\lambda) \wedge \lambda\}$$

$$\nu_{G(A)} = \sup \lambda_3 \{N_{g_A}(\lambda) \wedge \lambda\}$$

3.1 Proposition

$$1) \quad A \subseteq^{N_g} B \Leftrightarrow G(A) \subseteq G(B).$$

$$2) A =^{Ng} B \Leftrightarrow G(A) = G(B)$$

3.2 Definition

Let A be neutrosophic set of X. Then the neutrosophic complement of A generated by denoted by A^{Ngc} iff $[G(A)]^c$ may be defined as the following:

$$(Ng^{c1}) \langle x, \mu^c_A(x), \sigma^c_A(x), \nu^c_A(x) \rangle$$

$$(Ng^{c2}) \langle x, \nu_A(x), \sigma_A(x), \mu_A(x) \rangle$$

$$(Ng^{c3}) \langle x, \nu_A(x), \sigma^c_A(x), \mu_A(x) \rangle$$

3.1 Example. Let $X = \{x\}$, $A = \langle x, 0.5, 0.7, 0.6 \rangle$, $Ng_A = 1$, $Ng_A = 0$. Then $G(A) = \langle x, 0.5, 0.7, 0.6 \rangle$. Since our main purpose is to construct the tools for developing neutrosophic set and neutrosophic topology, we must introduce the $G(0_N)$ and $G(1_N)$ as follows $G(0_N)$ may be defined as:

$$i) G(0_N) = \langle x, 0, 0, 1 \rangle$$

$$ii) G(0_N) = \langle x, 0, 1, 1 \rangle$$

$$iii) G(0_N) = \langle x, 0, 1, 0 \rangle$$

$$iv) G(0_N) = \langle x, 0, 0, 0 \rangle$$

$G(1_N)$ may be defined as:

$$i) G(1_N) = \langle x, 1, 0, 0 \rangle$$

$$ii) G(1_N) = \langle x, 1, 0, 1 \rangle$$

$$iii) G(1_N) = \langle x, 1, 1, 0 \rangle$$

$$iv) G(1_N) = \langle x, 1, 1, 1 \rangle$$

We will define the following operations intersection and union for neutrosophic sets generated by Ng denoted by \cap^{Ng} and \cup^{Ng} respectively.

3.3 Definition. Let two neutrosophic sets $A = \langle x, \mu_A(x), \sigma_A(x), \nu_A(x) \rangle$ and

$B = \langle x, \mu_B(x), \sigma_B(x), \nu_B(x) \rangle$ on X, and

$$G(A) = \langle x, \mu_{G(A)}(x), \sigma_{G(A)}(x), \nu_{G(A)}(x) \rangle,$$

$G(B) = \langle x, \mu_{G(B)}(x), \sigma_{G(B)}(x), \nu_{G(B)}(x) \rangle$. Then $A \cap^{Ng} B$ may be defined as three types:

i) Type $G(A \cap B) =$

$$\langle \mu_{G(A)}(x) \wedge \mu_{G(B)}, \sigma_{G(A)}(x) \wedge \sigma_{G(B)}(x), \nu_{G(A)}(x) \vee \nu_{G(B)}(x) \rangle$$

ii) Type II:

$$G(A \cap B) =$$

$$\langle \mu_{G(A)}(x) \wedge \mu_{G(B)}, \sigma_{G(A)}(x) \vee \sigma_{G(B)}(x), \nu_{G(A)}(x) \vee \nu_{G(B)}(x) \rangle.$$

ii) Type III:

$$G(A \cap B) =$$

$$\langle \mu_{G(A)}(x) \times \mu_{G(B)}, \sigma_{G(A)}(x) \times \sigma_{G(B)}(x), \nu_{G(A)}(x) \times \nu_{G(B)}(x) \rangle$$

$A \cup^{Ng} B$ may be defined as two types:

Type I :

$$G(A \cup B) =$$

$$\langle \mu_{G(A)}(x) \vee \mu_{G(B)}, \sigma_{G(A)}(x) \wedge \sigma_{G(B)}(x), \nu_{G(A)}(x) \wedge \nu_{G(B)}(x) \rangle$$

Type II:

$$G(A \cup B) =$$

$$\langle \mu_{G(A)}(x) \vee \mu_{G(B)}, \sigma_{G(A)}(x) \vee \sigma_{G(B)}(x), \nu_{G(A)}(x) \wedge \nu_{G(B)}(x) \rangle$$

3.4 Definition

Let a neutrosophic set $A = \langle x, \mu_A(x), \sigma_A(x), \nu_A(x) \rangle$ and $G(A) = \langle x, \mu_{G(A)}(x), \sigma_{G(A)}(x), \nu_{G(A)}(x) \rangle$. Then

$$(1) []^{Ng} A = \langle x : \mu_{G(A)}(x), \sigma_{G(A)}(x), 1 - \nu_{G(A)}(x) \rangle$$

$$(2) \diamond^{Ng} A =$$

$$\langle x : 1 - \mu_{G(A)}(x), \sigma_{G(A)}(x), \nu_{G(A)}(x) \rangle$$

3.2 Proposition

For all two neutrosophic sets A and B on X generated by Ng, then the following are true

$$1) (A \cap B)^{cNg} = A^{cNg} \cup B^{cNg}.$$

$$2) (A \cup B)^{cNg} = A^{cNg} \cap B^{cNg}.$$

We can easily generalize the operations of intersection and union in definition 3.2 to arbitrary family of neutrosophic subsets generated by Ng as follows:

3.3 Proposition.

Let $\{A_j : j \in J\}$ be arbitrary family of neutrosophic subsets in X generated by two types , then

a) $\cap^{Ng} A_j$ may be defined as :

1) Type I :

$$G(\cap A_j) = \langle \wedge \mu_{G(A_j)}(x), \wedge \sigma_{G(A_j)}(x), \vee \nu_{G(A_j)}(x) \rangle,$$

2) Type II:

$$G(\cap A_j) = \langle \wedge \mu_{G(A_j)}(x), \vee \sigma_{G(A_j)}(x), \vee \nu_{G(A_j)}(x) \rangle,$$

b) $\cup^{Ng} A_j$ may be defined as :

$$1) G(\cup A_j) = \langle \vee \mu_{G(A_j)}(x), \wedge \sigma_{G(A_j)}(x), \wedge \nu_{G(A_j)}(x) \rangle \text{ or}$$

$$2) G(\cup A_j) = \left\langle \bigvee \mu_{G(A_j)}(x), \bigvee \sigma_{G(A_j)}(x), \bigwedge \nu_{G(A_j)}(x) \right\rangle.$$

3.4 Definition

Let $f: X \rightarrow Y$ be a mapping .

- (i) The image of a neutrosophic set A generated by Ψ on X under f is a neutrosophic set B on Y generated by Ψ , denoted by $f(A)$ whose reality function $g_B: Y \times I \rightarrow I=[0, 1]$ satisfies the property

$$\begin{aligned} \mu_{G(B)} &= \sup \lambda_1 \{Ng_A(\lambda) \wedge \lambda\} \\ \sigma_{G(B)} &= \sup \lambda_2 \{Ng_A(\lambda) \wedge \lambda\} \\ \nu_{G(B)} &= \sup \lambda_3 \{Ng_A(\lambda) \wedge \lambda\} \end{aligned}$$

- (ii) The preimage of a neutrosophic set B on Y generated by Ψ under f is a neutrosophic set A on X generated by Ψ , denoted by $f^{-1}(B)$, whose reality function $g_A: X \times [0, 1] \rightarrow [0, 1]$ satisfies the property $G(A) = G(f^{-1}(B)) \circ f$

3.4 Proposition

Let $\{A_j : j \in J\}$ and $\{B_j : j \in J\}$ be families of neutrosophic sets on X and Y generated by Ψ , respectively. Then for a function $f: X \rightarrow Y$, the following properties hold:

- (i) If $A_j \subseteq^{Ng} A_k ; i, j \in J$, then $f(A_j) \subseteq^{Ng} f(A_k)$
- (ii) If $B_j \subseteq^{Ng} B_k$, for $j, k \in J$, then

$$f^{-1}(B_j) \subseteq^{Ng} f^{-1}(B_k)$$

- (iii) $f^{-1}(\cup_{j \in J}^{Ng} B_j) = \cup_{j \in J}^{Ng} f^{-1}(B_j)$

3.5 Proposition

Let A and B be neutrosophic sets on X and Y generated by Ψ , respectively. Then, for a mappings $f: X \rightarrow Y$, we have :

- (i) $A \subseteq^{Ng} f^{-1}(f(A))$ (if f is injective the equality holds) .
- (ii) $f(f^{-1}(B)) \subseteq^{Ng} B$ (if f is surjective the equality holds) .
- (iii) $[f^{-1}(B)]^{Ngc} \subseteq^{Ng} f^{-1}(B^{Ngc})$.

3.5 Definition . Let X be a nonempty set, Ψ a family of neutrosophic sets generated by Ψ and let us use the notation

$$G(\Psi) = \{ G(A) : A \in \Psi \} .$$

If $(X, G(\Psi) = N\tau)$ is a neutrosophic topological space on X is Salama's sense [3], then we say that Ψ is a neutrosophic topology on X generated by Ψ and the pair (X, Ψ) is said to be a neutrosophic topological space generated by Ψ (ngts, for short). The elements in Ψ are called genuine neutrosophic open sets. also, we define the family

$$G(\Psi^c) = \{ 1 - G(A) : A \in \Psi \} .$$

3.6 Definition

Let (X, Ψ) be a ngts. A neutrosophic set C in X generated by Ψ is said to be a neutrosophic closed set generated by Ψ , if $1 - G(C) \in G(\Psi) = N\tau$.

3.7 Definition

Let (X, Ψ) be a ngts and A a neutrosophic set on X generated by Ψ . Then the neutrosophic interior of A generated by Ψ , denoted by, $ngintA$, is a set characterized by $G(intA) = \int_{G(\Psi)} G(A)$, where $\int_{G(\Psi)}$

denotes the interior operation in neutrosophic topological spaces generated by Ψ . Similarly, the neutrosophic closure of A generated by Ψ , denoted by $ngclA$, is a neutrosophic set characterized by $G(ngclA) = \overset{cl}{G(\Psi)} G(A)$

, where $\overset{cl}{G(\Psi)}$ denotes the closure operation in

neutrosophic topological spaces generated by Ψ .

The neutrosophic interior $ngint(A)$ and the genuine neutrosophic closure $ngclA$ generated by Ψ can be characterized by :

$$ngintA =^{Ng} \cup^{Ng} \{ U : U \in \Psi \text{ and } U \subseteq^{Ng} A \}$$

$$ngclA =^{Ng} \cap^{Ng} \{ C : C \text{ is neutrosophic closed generated by } \Psi \text{ and } A \subseteq^{Ng} C \}$$

Since : $G(ngint A) = \cup \{ G(U) : G(U) \in G(\Psi), G(U) \subseteq G(A) \}$

$$G(ngcl A) = \cap \{ G(C) : G(C) \in G(\Psi^c), G(A) \subseteq G(C) \}.$$

3.6 Proposition . For any neutrosophic set A generated by (X, Ψ) on a NTS (X, Ψ) , we have

$$(i) \text{cl } A^{Ngc} = Ng (\text{int } A)^{Ngc}$$

$$(ii) \text{Int } A^{Ngc} = Ng (\text{cl } A)^{Ngc}$$

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